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Historical Sciences

SPORTS-RECREATION ACTIVITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION: HISTORY AND MODERNITY

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Abstract

The article examines sports and recreation activities in Russian universities in a historical retrospective. The deteriorating health of the younger generation, poor physical fitness of students require new approaches to the professional training of future teachers at the university, which is associated with the need to improve the literacy of teachers in the field of physical culture and sports. The article pays special attention to historical innovations in the field of understanding physical culture and sports activity, in which the creative interaction of a teacher and a student, the formation of a personality with values, needs, interests, motives is associated with regular physical exercises, which are considered a common and important feature of physical education.

Keywords: sport, university, society, state, people.

I. INTRODUCTION

In higher educational institutions, "Physical culture" is presented as an academic discipline and the most important component of the holistic development of the individual. Being a part of the general culture, psychophysical formation and professional training of the student during the entire period of study, "Physical culture" is among the compulsory disciplines of the cycle "General humanities and socio-economic disciplines".

Physical Culture performs its educational and developmental functions most fully in the purposeful pedagogical process of physical education, which is based on the basic general didactic principles: consciousness, visibility, accessibility, systematicity and dynamism. It is these principles that permeate the entire content of the 'exemplary curriculum for universities in the academic discipline "Physical Culture", the development of which is closely connected not only with the physical development and improvement of the functional systems of the body of a young person, but also with the formation of vital mental qualities, properties and personality traits by means of physical culture and sports. All this in general is reflected in the psychophysical reliability of the future specialist, in the necessary level of stability of his professional performance.

The socio-humanitarian orientation of physical culture in general and, especially, in educational institutions of all levels is the main principle provision of the Federal Law "On Physical Culture and Sports in the Russian Federation". This provision is taken as a basis and specified in special orders of the Ministry of Education of Russia.

II. METHODOLOGY

The need for an integrated approach to the analysis of the processes of formation of physical culture of students led to the appeal to the possibilities of interdisciplinary research. The sociological analysis of the studied problem from the standpoint of the socio-cultural approach allows us to consider culture and sociality mutually conditioned. In determining the relationship between physical culture, the system of value orientations and social norms, the methodological basis is the work of P. A. Sorokin, who considers "personality, society and culture as an inseparable triad." The works of M. Weber and T. Parsons are methodologically significant for identifying and substantiating the priority of value orientations, the normativity of fixing a healthy lifestyle in the process of forming the physical culture of modern students.

III. DISCUSSION

The tradition of defining the concept of "culture" is represented by several theoretical directions. The dynamic nature of culture is emphasized by E. Baller, V.K. Balsevich, A.A. Guzhalovsky, V.E. Davidovich, N. Zlobin, M.S. Kagan, J.H. Kogan, Z.I. Kuznetsova, E.S. Markaryan, V.M. Mezhujev, I.V. Muravov, V.N. Platonov, B.C. Farfel, O. Khanova, H.H. Yakovlev, considering it as a process of development of the "essential forces" of a person who is a subject of the cultural and historical process. From these positions, culture is considered as a way of activity that gives human activity an internal integrity and a special kind of orientation, as well as a way of regulating, preserving, reproducing and developing the entire social life.

Many authors, including S. Anisimov, Y.R. Vishnevsky, O. Dzhioev, N.S. Ladyzhets, A.B. Merenkova, N. Chavchavadze, V.T. Shapko, understand culture as a system of artificial activity programs that are essential, generic characteristics of human activity.

The analysis of the system of value orientations is presented in the works of A.G. Zdravomyslov, N. Sladyzhets, B.C. Merlin, V.N. Myasishchev, V.B. Olshansky, B.C. Prangishvili, I.A. Surina, D.N. Uznadze, V.A. Yadov, K. Klakhon, T. Opport, M. Rokich, R. Sheldon, E. Shils. They consider value orientations as a leading factor in the formation of the culture of social subjects.

Such researchers as I.M. Arshavsky, B. Valkov, V.M. Zatsiorsky, A.A. Loginov, V.V. Petrovsky, V.P. Filin. A. focus on the diverse components of physical culture, the forms and types of which are presented through the prism of clarifying their role, place and relationships in the general system of factors aimed at optimizing the physical condition and development of a person. They studied the role, place, relationship of the components of physical culture in the general system of factors optimizing the physical condition and development of a person.

IV. RESULTS

Physical education of students as a pedagogical system of physical improvement of a person remains a key concept for general comprehensive education and, especially, in the formation of a person's physical culture. In universities, the contribution of education in the field of physical culture should consist in providing students with all aspects of knowledge about human life, about his health and a healthy lifestyle, as well as

mastering practical skills and abilities that ensure the development and improvement of the personality itself. Negative tendencies characterizing the level of physical development and health status of student youth, skeptical attitude of students to the principles of a healthy lifestyle, their ignorance of the means and possibilities of physical culture and sports for full and active leisure, - sports activities. A qualitative rethinking and creative reforming of the process of physical education by strengthening the humanitarian direction of physical culture significantly increases its culture-forming essence and provides a basis for a constructive solution to this problem.

Socio-economic and political transformations of modern Russia create conditions for the formation of physical culture and sports activity of young people by giving everyone the freedom to choose the types, means and forms of organizing their own physical activity, taking into account individual characteristics, morphological and functional characteristics and socio-psychological factors, his values, interests and needs. The health-improving potential of physical culture and sports is a powerful stimulus for students' physical culture and sports activity.

The problem of assessing the state of individual health of a person and monitoring changes in its level is becoming increasingly important, especially for people exposed to high psycho-emotional and physical stress. A radical conceptual transition in health care policy is required from considering citizens as passive consumers of medical services to an awareness of the need to strengthen the physical and mental health of a person through the joint efforts of the state, public organizations and individuals. The formation of individual, personality-oriented health improvement programs aimed at strengthening the health of a particular person, improving his adaptation to educational and work activities has not yet found its place in educational systems, including in higher educational institutions.

For the preservation and development of spiritual, intellectual and physical potential, mankind throughout its development forms the appropriate social institutions. In the preservation of human spirituality, it is difficult to overestimate the role of religion, art, literature. Intellectual potential is preserved and developed by the education and training system, science. Responsible for physical potential are physical education and sports, health care, the system of recreational activities.

V. CONCLUSION

It is obvious that the contribution of physical culture education to general higher education should consist in providing students with all aspects of knowledge about human life, about his health and a healthy lifestyle, as well as mastering the entire arsenal of practical skills and abilities that ensure the preservation and strengthening of health, development and improvement. his psychophysical abilities and personality traits. Only such a humanitarian direction of physical culture in a university can serve as the basis for a significant increase in its culture-forming functions.

With the help of the knowledge gained in the discipline "Physical culture", students must create a holistic idea of the processes and phenomena occurring in living nature, more fully understand the possibilities of modern scientific methods of cognition of nature and master them at the level of professional functions. The knowledge obtained during the development of the mandatory minimum content of the program material on physical culture should form the basis of ideas about a healthy lifestyle and provide a theoretical basis for the formation of skills and abilities for physical self-improvement of a person throughout his life. This approach to physical education of students entails a rejection of the traditional models of the university pedagogical process and the need to revise the goals of the physical culture process towards the development of its humanizing and culture-forming functions at the present stage.

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СПОРТИВНО-ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ В ВЫСШЕЙ ШКОЛЕ: ИСТОРИЯ И СОВРЕМЕННОСТЬ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматривается спортивно-оздоровительная деятельность в вузах России в исторической ретроспективе. Ухудшение здоровья подрастающего поколения, плохая физическая подготовка студентов требуют новых подходов к профессиональной подготовке будущих преподавателей в вузе, что связано с необходимостью повышения грамотности преподавателей в области физической культуры и спорта. В статье особое внимание уделяется историческим инновациям в области понимания физической культуры и спортивной деятельности, в которых творческое взаимодействие преподавателя и студента, формирование личности с ценностями, потребностями, интересами, мотивами связано с регулярными физическими упражнениями, которые считаются общей и важной особенностью физического воспитания.

Ключевые слова: спорт, университет, общество, государство, люди.

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